

A Case Study: Stunting in Kalibukbuk Tourism Village

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Abstract

Introduction: The territories area of Puskesmas Buleleng 1 and 2 is not far from the city center, but still has a number of cases of malnutrition children. Three toddlers were identified as stunting in kalibukbuk village and Tukadmungga. Kalibukbuk village is a tourist village located near by Lovina tourism center. The pandemic period has been a heavy blow to the communities of tourist areas, one of which is Kalibukbuk village. Many factors should be involved to solve the stunting problems, one is family support, specially family medicine with holistic approach is needed to prevent stunting. **Purpose:** this study aimed to describe several factors related to stunting in toddlers in Kalibukbuk Tourism Village. **Method:** this is a descriptive qualitative design. Datas were collected through in-depth interviews and observations. Deep interviews with 3 important informants showed that it has not improve in 1 year of program supervision. **Result:** Four domains were identified: knowledge, family income funds, cultural related issues and health worker's activity. These encompassed a variety of reasons which could explain the malnutrition in children of those kalibukbuk village. **Conclusion:** The conclusion of this study is that there are several factors that affect the incidence of stunting are: reinforcing factors (knowledge and availability of time), enabling factors (availability of funds, socio-economic) and reinforcing factors (feeding process, Family Support and health workers). All of the above factors in this case in the category of inadequate to support and strengthen the eradication of stunting.

Keywords: Stunting, Children, Qualitative Study, Buleleng

INTRODUCTION

Healthy life should starts with the smallest unit of society, that is the family. The family approach is seen as one of the effective ways to overcome health problems. This is because the family has a big role in optimizing the growth, development, and productivity of all its members through meeting nutritional and health needs. The implementation of family health efforts aims to realize quality families who live in a healthy condition. In addition to a family healthy state, another requirement needed in forming a quality family is the health condition of each member. The health

condition of mothers and children is an important indicator in the implementation of Family Health efforts. Mothers and children are vulnerable groups related to the phase of pregnancy, childbirth and puerperium in the mother and the phase of growth and development in the child. This causes the health of mothers and children to receive priority in the implementation of family health efforts.

Children's health problems today are faced with the incidence of cases of stunting in children. Data in Asia, Indonesia is ranked 2nd in the number of stunting cases.

Picture 1. Prevention of Stunting in children under five years of age (2020) source: Asian Development Bank, 2021

An indicator of a child's health is nutritional status. For the data recorded in Buleleng regency, there is a recording of weight according to age group (BB/U) and height according to age group (TB / U). Undernutrition and malnutrition is a nutritional status based on the weight index according to age (BB/U). In 2020, from 28,688 toddlers (0 - 59 months)

weighed in Buleleng regency, there were 1,064 malnourished toddlers (3.7%). There were 2,057 short toddlers out of 28,573 toddlers (0-59 months) measured height (7.2%). Meanwhile, the percentage of underweight toddlers was 2.4% or 679 underweight toddlers out of 28,610 toddlers (0-59 months) measured. In chart 2, stunting case shows as blue plots.

Picture 2. Nutritional Status Of Buleleng Toddlers In 2020
Sumber: Profil Kesehatan Kabupaten Buleleng Tahun 2020

Malnutrition is the nutritional status according to weight (BB) and height (TB) with Z-score <-3 and or with clinical signs (marasmus, kwashiorkor). In 2020, 34 cases of malnutrition toddlers were found. Kubutambahan became the only sub-district in Buleleng regency that did not

have cases of malnutrition in 2020. The whole case of malnourished toddlers has been getting treatment. The working area of Public health centres or Called Puskesmas (Puskesmas Buleleng 1 and 2) located at a distance not far from the city center is still a supporter of cases of

malnutrition toddlers. For malnourished toddlers at Puskesmas Buleleng 2, namely in Kalibukbuk village and Tukadnungga, a number of 3 toddlers, have been categorized as stunting. When viewed from the condition of the region, then Kalibukbuk village is a tourist village with Lovina tourism center. Some people work as fishermen and employees in accommodation and tourism transportation.

Aspects that affect the nutritional status of a person that can be from the consumption of food obtained, education and knowledge of a person about the importance of meeting the nutritional intake of the body, socio-economic family is also very instrumental in meeting the nutritional needs of a person, the characteristics of a person such as male sex is generally preferred in the fulfillment of food intake, environmental factors also provide a large role because a bad environment can trigger infectious diseases that will affect a person's health.

The causes of stunting do not last just like that, but stunting is a condition of malnutrition problems that occurred in the past starting from adolescence that has experienced malnutrition, continued during pregnancy lack of intake, until the birth of a baby experiencing malnutrition and continues into the next life cycle. Factors related to the incidence of stunting include income, work, family, history of exclusive breastfeeding and low birth weight history.

In addition, parenting related to nutrition is also very influential on nutritional status. In a study by previous researchers, where the results obtained nutritional parenting affect the nutritional status of school-age children in schools in Buleleng.

Based on data from the Health Office, there were 1 tourist village contributing stunting cases in 2019. This stunting incident is also a concern because this tourist village is a working area of the

Buleleng 2 Health Center which is classified as rural-urban which is less than 30 km from the city center of Buleleng regency.

Based on the above data, it is necessary to conduct research on factors related to the incidence of stunting in toddlers in the Kalibukbuk Tourism Village area. The pandemic period has been a heavy blow to the communities of tourist areas, one of which is Kalibukbuk village. From the report of health workers at the Puskesmas Buleleng 2, toddlers in other villages have been able to catch up with stunting but not so with toddlers in Kalibukbuk Tourism Village. Therefore, researchers conducted a stunting case study in Kalibukbuk Tourism Village.

METHODS

This study is a qualitative descriptive study to determine several risk factors that include age, sex, maternal education level, history of low birth weight (LBW), and a history of exclusive breastfeeding (called Air Susu Ibu- ASI). Data collection was carried out from March to July 2022 through secondary data from Puskesmas Buleleng 2. By using qualitative descriptive data will be obtained risk factors as well as how the interaction between factors that affect stunting. Promer Data was also obtained through interviews from stunting cases in Kalibukbuk village during the period of research implementation. Informants are individuals who are willing to be the subject of research and fill out informed consent. Data collection used in this study is through in-depth interviews. The process of data analysis using thematic data analysis.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1. Characteristic Factors

Stunting case in Kalibukbuk village is a case that founded by Health Worker's at public health center (Puskesmas) Buleleng 2 in measurement as routine in

"POSYANDU" (a promotive and preventive event held routine per month). In 2021, 3 stunting cases were found, namely 2 cases in the tukadmungga Village area and 1 in the Kalibukbuk tourist village. Case in kalibukbuk village with the current age of 28 months, women with Body Weight 9, 1 kg, Length 80.8 cm. Gender is boy, as the third son of 3 Siblings. The child lives with his father, mother and grandmother along with 2 siblings in a house whose condition is low level of healthy environment.

Based on Anthropometric measurement of patients in accordance with the regulation of the Indonesian Minister of Health No. 2 Year 2020 on child Antopometry standards, it can be concluded that:

1. According to the measurement of BB / U patients are in the category of underweight (underweight)
 2. According to the measurement of TB / U patients are in the category of short (stunted)
 3. According to the measurement of BB/TB patients are in the category of good nutrition (normal)
2. Predisposing factors

Predisposing factors in this study are factors that support the actions derived from the respondents. Based on the results of in-depth interviews with respondents, namely parents and grandmother of children. Predisposing factors that affect the incidence of stunting in toddlers in this study were analyzed with thematic components of behavior is knowledge. The results showed the knowledge of fathers, mothers and grandmothers about toddler nutrition. The three respondents did not know about good nutrition for children as quoted below:

"I don't know about stunting...what I see is my child's body is small" (Father) " I find my child is small, maybe because my child does not consume milk and eating is difficult, but the movement is active " (mother)

"I see my grandson's body is small like his father used to be smaller thsn other children but he is active" (grandmother)

Based on the results showed that the level of knowledge of informants about stunting is one of the factors associated with stunting. The quote above shows stunting in children under five is not known as an abnormal condition so it needs to be watched out for by parents and caregivers.

These results are similar to studies conducted on mothers of stunting cases in Indonesia that show maternal knowledge of nutrition is a significant risk factor for stunting events (Sari, 2021; Pradana, 2021). Knowledge of nutrition is the initial factor in behavior change improvement of nutritional status, so knowledge is an internal factor that affects behavior change. The mother's knowledge of nutrition will determine the mother's behavior in providing food for her child. Mothers with good nutritional knowledge can provide food with the right type and amount to support the growth and development of toddlers. Providing the right ingredients and menus for toddlers in an effort to improve nutritional status will be realized if the mother has a good level of nutritional knowledge (Sarma, 2017). Ignorance of information about nutrition can cause lack of quality or nutritional quality of family food, especially food consumed by toddlers (Reiher,2019). One of the causes of nutritional disorders is a lack of nutritional knowledge and a person's ability to reach information about nutrition in daily life. The level of nutritional knowledge of the mother affects the attitude and behavior in choosing Foodstuffs, which will further affect the nutritional state of her family. (Kodish, 2019). Another factor that stands out is that mother do not give exclusive breastfeeding to their children. The results of interviews with the mother showed that the reason mother who do not give exclusive breastfeeding to their children

because the mother considers her milk inadequate volume so it needs to be given additional formula milk. Mother also give additional cookies and porridge (called MP ASI) earlier before 6 months old because the perception of mother and grandmother who think their children are still hungry when breastfed. In addition, another reason is because mothers go to work leaving their children more than 8 hours at home.

"It's hard, we can't keep breastfeeding, let alone have to be pumped and collect. Not much to get, even though the baby needs a lot of milk, so that we add with formula milk "(Mother)" at the age of 3 months ..we start giving the mild porridge "(grandmother)

"Yes I actually know exclusive breastfeeding is important, but my breastfeed production is low so I prefer to give a boiled rice water when we cant buy some formula's milk "(Mother) The results of this study are similar to some research results stating that exclusive breastfeeding for less than 6 months contributes to the incidence of stunting toddlers in Indonesia. (Satiawati, 2018; Beal, T. 2018). Breast milk has many benefits, namely increasing children's immunity to disease, ear infections, reducing the frequency of diarrhea, chronic constipation and ileus (Henningham and McGregor, 2009). Lack of breastfeeding and complementary feeding too early can increase the risk of stunting, especially in early life (Adair and Guilkey, 1997). The magnitude of the effect of exclusive breastfeeding on the nutritional status of children makes WHO recommends implementing interventions to increase breastfeeding during the first 6 months as one of the steps to achieve WHO Global Nutrition Targets 2025 on reducing the number of stunting in children under five years (WHO, 2012).

3. Enabling factor

This factors as a prominent enabling factor, one of each is the amount of funds

or salary. This is influenced by the socioeconomic level of respondents. Half of the respondents have an income that fluctuates between 750 thousand to 1 million rupiah. In addition, three respondents live with extended families, that have a number of family members more than five people. This certainly affects the variety and number of the needs and costs of family life including food. The low socio-economic level affects the diversity of the types of food offered to the child. This is important when the child refuses the offered food. When no other type of food is available, the child will be allowed to eat with what is or not to eat. Like the quote below:" if you have money, good nutrition if you don't want to eat, I usually immediately give vitamins or the menu doesn't change "(mother)"..if the mother works, just a potluck, what is there I give " (grandmother) the results of this study are in line with research in Karangasem, Bali in 2017 which found that low income is a risk factor for stunting in toddlers. (Muhammad, S., 2017) low economic Status has a significant impact on the likelihood of children becoming thin and short (UNICEF, 2019). Tisna's research (2021) shows that families with good economic status will be able to get better public services such as education, health services, road access, and others so that it can affect the nutritional status of children. In addition, family purchasing power will increase so that family access to food will be better. Another factor is the lack of availability of family foodstuffs. The results of research conducted, it is known that the food that is always available at home is rice, and chip. Sometime they can buy some eggs. Often the consumption of respondents is rice, chips and vegetables. The consumption of chicken or eggs is not every day or routine in a week. This Lack of Foodstuffs is caused by the low knowledge of balanced nutrition and the culture of the diet as it is

for some respondents as a result of low income.

As in the statement: "he does not like meat, chicken and egg, he prefer to take rice with chips "(mother)" every day eat porridge with spinach or carrots, sometimes eggs sometimes chicken, or pindang (salted fish) "(grandmother) "eat meat only occasionally because it is expensive. Our income by salary only will not be enough for get it" (father)

The results obtained in this study are in line with the results of Hermina (2011) and Widyaningsih (2018) who found that the availability of family food is related to stunting. Family food availability is one indicator of the fulfillment of nutritional needs in toddlers. Food availability is the ability to access food and provide household food. Food availability is also related to food security at household level. Food availability is related to the production and distribution of foodstuffs in sufficient quantities from the producer to the household level. The availability of food in the household also pays attention to the quality and nutritional content. An indicator of sufficient food availability is the quality of the food itself. This means that the population can consume micronutrients, both vitamins and minerals, which are sufficient to be able to live a healthy life. Food consumption in each household expenditure group has increased in the types of food that are of better quality. The availability of food in the household that is not not enough will have an impact on the intake is also low so that the nutritional needs of toddlers are not met. The quality of food available in the household is also an important factor that is the principle of food availability. Good food quality will increase the quantity and quality of intake in the household.

4. Reinforcing Factors

Reinforcing factors in this study in the form of family support in the feeding of toddlers. Some respondents lack help from

other family members in doing homework so mothers are too busy and have limited time. This is influenced by the patriarchal culture that occurs in Indonesia where household chores are only done by the mother, only the father works so that if on holidays the father only helps and even then only when asked. After all my household work is done, i will take care of my son's feed but while I am still doing some works, his grandmother who often help me take care of children.

This is in line with Anita's research (2012) in Simeule regency, Aceh province which states that there is a significant relationship between toddlers who do not get family support and stunting. Children who did not receive family support were shown to increase the incidence of stunting 2.9 times compared to children who received family support. Stunting prevention efforts need to be improved to reduce the incidence of stunting and prevent the impact caused. The role of parents is very important, namely by giving exclusive breastfeeding, proper complementary feeding, and maintaining sanitary hygiene so that toddlers get adequate nutrition from an early age and avoid infectious diseases. While the role of health workers is also no less important such as village midwives and posyandu cadres, namely reminding and alerting parents to do this, disseminating health nutrition education to pregnant women and parents of toddlers, monitoring the growth of infants every month at posyandu.

"health workers, midwife, shouldn't only there in posyandu, so will only already once a month this year my child continues to be visited dikasi additional food,, but my child does not want to consume it because already know the food is more delicious as snacks "(mother)

"it should be porridge and rice and raw materials are better given to us, because my grandson rarely eat chicken, meat and

fresh fish because it is expensive”
(grandmother)

CONCLUSION

The conclusion of this study is that there are several factors that affect the incidence of stunting are: reinforcing factors (knowledge and availability of time), enabling factors (availability of funds, socio-economic) and reinforcing factors (feeding process, Family Support and health workers). All health workers in order to provide adequate information about the importance of awareness children nutrition and growth and development. The promotive information can be provided through counseling to adolescents, mothers during pregnancy, postpartum and breastfeeding during the mother's visit to the Antenatal Care, attending classes for pregnant women, and always scheduling the home visits.

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